

Rayada B3—a high-yielding, ufra-resistant deepwater rice for Assam, India

D. Das, N.K. Sarma, R. Borgohain, and P. Das, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Assam Agricultural University, P.O. Boisa Garumuria, North Lakhimpur, Pin 787001, Assam, India

Of the 2 million ha of rice land affected by flood every year in Assam, India, 490,000 are planted to deepwater rice. During the long growing period from March to December, deepwater rice is exposed to attacks by different pests and diseases. Among them, infestation by rice stem nematode, *Ditylenchus angustus*, commonly called ufra disease, is considered a major problem, causing a 30–100% yield loss.

Several deepwater and semi-deepwater rice varieties were screened for resistance to ufra nematode during 1991–92 under field conditions at RARS. Among the entries tested, a few Rayada selections collected from Bangladesh, such as Rayada 16-06, Rayada 16-09, and Rayada B3, were resistant to ufra in Assam. These lines were further screened for ufra resistance and yielding ability in a replicated trial from 1993 to 1997 in diseased and disease-free areas. The diseased plot was selected from a naturally infested field and ufra disease pressure was further increased by adding inoculum at sowing, whereas earthen bunds around the field kept the control plot ufra-free. Table 1 presents the panicle infestation rate and grain yield per hectare of the lines over the years. Statistical analysis (3 RBD) followed after transformation of percentage infestation data.

All the lines exhibited significant variation in ufra infestation and yield. Rayada 16-06, Rayada 16-09, and Rayada B3 had good resistance to the nematode with 10.0%, 12.6%, and 18.8% mean panicle infestation rates, respectively. On the other hand, susceptible check variety Rangabao was severely affected (80.9%). Simultaneously, Rayada B3 showed a higher average mean yield (0.95 t ha⁻¹) than the other three varieties in ufra-endemic areas. Table 2 shows the mean yield of lines over years in the ufra-free area. Under ufra-free con-

ditions also, Rayada B3 outyielded all three varieties with a mean average yield of 2.0 t ha⁻¹. Rayada B3 had a 22% yield advantage over Rangabao.

Rayada B3 is a photoperiod-sensitive and tall but nonelongating deepwater rice that can withstand up to 1.5 m water depth, with a mean height of 150 cm. Its grains are heavier (29 g 1,000 grains⁻¹) and coarse and the kernels are red. Rayada B3 yielded 0.2–0.4 t ha⁻¹ under direct-seeded

conditions and 0.5 t ha⁻¹ under transplanted conditions.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank the Director of Research (Agriculture), Assam Agricultural University, and the Chief Scientist, RARS, North Lakhimpur, Assam, for providing facilities for the study.

Table 1. Panicle infestation rate and yield of ufra-resistant lines in ufra-endemic hot spots of RARS, North Lakhimpur, Assam, 1993–97.

Variety	Panicle infestation rate (%) and grain yield (t ha ⁻¹) ^a					Mean
	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	
Rayada B3	19.1 (0.8)	12.5 (1.0)	26.5 (0.9)	14.4 (1.1)	21.2 (na)	18.8 (0.9)
Rayada 16-06	9.4 (0.8)	8.5 (0.5)	14.5 (0.4)	9.8 (0.6)	21.0 (na)	12.6 (0.6)
Rayada 16-09	8.7 (0.6)	8.2 (0.5)	11.2 (0.4)	6.7 (0.5)	15.6 (na)	10.1 (0.5)
Rangabao (susceptible check)	60.6 (0.8)	80.3 (0.6)	95.5 (0.2)	72.7 (0.6)	95.2 (na)	80.9 (0.6)
CD (0.5%)	8.2 (0.9)	6.4 (1.2)	3.9 (0.9)	8.7 (0.7)	2.7 (–)	

^aNumbers in parentheses are grain yield. na = not available.

Table 2. Yield of Rayada lines in ufra-free area of RARS, North Lakhimpur, Assam, 1993–97.

Variety	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)					Mean
	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	
Rayada B3	1.0	2.2	2.2	2.0	2.4	2.0
Rayada 16-06	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.8	0.8
Rayada 16-09	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.5
Rangabao	1.3	1.7	1.8	1.4	1.9	1.6
CD (0.5%)	1.05	1.15	0.83	0.99	0.93	

For everything you want to know about one of the world's longest running cereals

Produced by the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI), Philippines, in association with the West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA), Cotê d'Ivoire, and the Centro Internacional Agricultura Tropical (CIAT), Colombia.
<http://www.riceweb.org>